

Top 5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

(2020-2022)

The Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) is a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) that promotes high-quality and trusted social science research. CESSDA and its Service Providers (SPs) (i.e., national social science data archives) are from 22 member countries. We offer integrated and sustainable data services by connecting national data archives across Europe.

This brief highlights the progress and impact of CESSDA through the key performance indicators (KPIs) collected on its SPs between 2020 and 2022, showcasing our achievements in the following areas:

1. Enable access to **38K** primary digital objects (including data) through at least **650K** publications
2. Support over **100** multidisciplinary projects for the digital future of Europe and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
3. Empower education in over **300** lectures and build research capacity of **12K** attendees
4. Engage over **9 million** visits through websites and tools to enhance research transparency
5. Optimise return on investment in social science research by enabling data reuse

CESSDA as a Landmark of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) illustrates its scientific relevance and credibility within the European Research Area. CESSDA supports researchers in discovering and assessing over 37K datasets in national languages, through tools such as the European Language Social Science Thesaurus, Vocabulary Service, and Data Catalogue. We provide extensive training to foster the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for research data. We contribute to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the advancement of SDGs through participation in diverse projects.

Collectively advancing frontier research: KPIs of CESSDA SPs

1 Enhance access to data and publications

Primary digital objects – each consisting of dataset, metadata, documentation, and unique persistent identifier – are the most important output of data archives. By 2022, CESSDA SPs made **38K primary digital objects** available – which were used in at least **650K publications** (e.g., scientific articles, reports, and policy briefs). This represents increasing interest in publishing research data. These resources contribute to uncovering insights into human behaviour and societal change. Moreover, CESSDA SPs supports the FAIR principles – we encourage data reuse by creating clear metadata and improving open-source data assessment tools, e.g., [F-UJI](#).

Note: Data on publications has only been collected since 2021.

2 Support multidisciplinary research for the digital future of Europe and the SDGs

Between 2020 and 2022, CESSDA actively contributed to the digital future of Europe and the SDGs through project partnership and collaboration with the research community and other ERICs. These research projects include [HumMingBird](#) to inform migration patterns and policy (SDG 10), [BY-COVID](#) to improve pandemics preparedness (SDGs 3 and 9), and [COORDINATE](#) to enhance children and youth well-being (SDGs 3, 4, and 5).¹ In 2022, CESSDA SPs participated in **102 projects** beyond the CESSDA funding framework, representing a **28% increase** in external project engagement from 2021.

1. [17 Sustainable Development Goals \(SDGs\)](#) were adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015 as an urgent call to action by all countries. Although CESSDA projects promote all SDGs, the selected example projects focus on SDG 3 (good health and well-being), SDG 4 (quality education), SDG 5 (gender equality), SDG 9 (industry, innovation, and infrastructure), and SDG 10 (reduced inequalities).

3 Empower education and build research capacity

In 2022, CESSDA SPs presented at **642 events** including conferences, symposiums, webinars, face-to-face workshops, and seminars. In addition, CESSDA SPs organised **341 training and education events** which were attended by **12K researchers, research data managers, and other data users**. Our attendees gain practical knowledge on interdisciplinary research, data management, open science practices, and the latest data protection legislation.

Note: Edu. stands for education.

4 Improve public engagement and enhance research transparency

In 2022, CESSDA attracted **over 9 million** visits to all websites and tools. The median number of visits across the 22 SPs **increased by 170%** between 2021 and 2022. By assessing the reach and depth of our engagement, we design tools and services tailored to our community's needs.

Note: The median is presented to account for the variations and outliers across SPs.

5 Optimise return on investment in social science research

CESSDA is a growing community in the context of increasing demand for FAIR data and long-term data preservation. In 2022, the median number of staff at SPs **increased by 30%** from 2021; the median annual funding at national data archives (covering both salary costs and other operational expenses) amounts to **250K EUR**. However, variations in staff roles and salary costs across the 22 SPs make direct comparisons challenging. Despite these variations, CESSDA remains committed to improving data openness and transparency for reproducible research.

Note: The median is presented to account for the variations and outliers across SPs.

Looking forward

CESSDA and its SPs will collect impact stories that go beyond existing quantitative metrics, focusing on **citations**, **user needs**, and **researcher engagement**, to demonstrate our commitment to diverse stakeholders.

We invite and encourage new collaborations in Europe and internationally to leverage the impact of social science data. We also count on further financial and technical commitments to promoting open science for sustainable development.

Data limitations

The data presented in this brief were collected between 2020 and 2022 from 22 SPs. It is important to note that there are significant differences across SPs in terms of governance, resource capacity, and digital infrastructure. The data were collected during the COVID-19 pandemic with restrictions on social distancing, travel, and curfews. These circumstances may influence data archiving, training, and research practices. The differences across SPs and over time affect the consistency and comparability of the data. Although every effort has been made to ensure data accuracy, the numbers should be interpreted as indicative rather than strictly comparable across SPs and years. These variations highlight the need for contextual information when interpreting the results.

CESSDA is a community representing **22 member and 12 partner countries** that share expertise and technology

The 22 member countries dedicate tremendous time and effort in leveraging Open Science practices, collecting C-KPI data regularly, and addressing the needs of data users. They are Austria (AUSSDA), Belgium (SODHA), Croatia (CROSSDA), Czechia (ČSDA), Finland (FSD), France (Progedo), Germany (GESIS), Greece (So.Da.Net), Hungary (TÁRKI), Iceland (DATICE), Ireland (ISSDA), Italy (DASSI), the Netherlands (DANS), North Macedonia (MK DASS), Norway (Sikt), Portugal (APIS), Serbia (DCS), Slovak Republic (SASD), Slovenia (ADP), Sweden (SND), Switzerland (FORS), and the United Kingdom (UKDS).

The 12 partner countries collaborate with member countries to enable the research community to conduct high-quality social science research. They are Albania (ADAS), Bosnia and Herzegovina (Data Archive for Social Sciences), Bulgaria (The National Data Service), Estonia (University of Tartu Library), Kosovo (KSSDC), Latvia (RSU), Lithuania (LiDA), Luxembourg (LISER), Montenegro (MSSDA), Poland (PADS), Romania (RODA), and Ukraine (Kyiv archive).

Together, the CESSDA community increases the scientific excellence and efficacy of social science research.

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